

JustMIP: Advancing Climate Justice Considerations in IAM Scenarios

A model intercomparison project protocol prepared by IIASA, with contributions from ELEVATE project partners and informed by feedback from diverse stakeholder engagement activities across both Non-Annex I and Annex I countries, as well as input from external collaborators. For more information please contact: justmip@iiasa.ac.at

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1. Introduction

Climate change mitigation scenarios developed using Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have been foundational to shaping the solution space informing global climate policy deliberations (Pirani et al. 2024). As their scope expands to include new technologies (Gidden, Brutschin, et al. 2023; Strefler et al. 2021, 2025), demand-side interventions (Grubler et al. 2018; van Heerden et al. 2025), institutional dynamics (Bertram et al. 2024; Bi et al. 2023), and a broader set of sustainable development goals (Soergel et al. 2021, 2024) including biodiversity targets and ecosystem integrity (Leclère et al. 2020b; von Jeetze et al. 2023), IAMs can also advance beyond their prevailing reliance on ex-post assessments of equity, fairness, and justice considerations¹ (Pachauri et al. 2022; van den Berg et al. 2019; S. Pachauri et al. 2026). This advance is necessary to address gaps in the solution space that are critical to contemporary climate and sustainable development policy deliberations (see Zimm et al. (2024) for a recent overview). Emerging needs call for a greater range of scenarios integrating justice considerations such as differentiated efforts and costs of capital, the examination of intergenerational justice, and the design of sustainable development pathways towards higher wellbeing convergence (Battiston et al. 2021; Bauer et al. 2020; Clift and Kuzemko 2024; Emmerling et al. 2019; Gilli et al. 2024; Hickel and Slamersak 2022; Jafino et al. 2021; Kanitkar et al. 2024; Pachauri et al. 2022; Rubiano Rivadeneira and Carton 2022; Zimm et al. 2024).

This protocol outlines a systematic approach to integrate an initial set of underrepresented justice considerations into global IAMs and examine their interactions, contributing to ongoing community efforts to expand the solution space informing climate and sustainable development policy deliberations. This work is informed by an assessment of critiques and conceptual advances identified in the recent literature, as well as by expert elicitation with modelling and non-modelling experts conducted under the ELEVATE project (Low et al. 2025). Consistent with expert input, we underline that explicitly incorporating justice considerations, as proposed here, should not be interpreted to imply that other scenarios are necessarily inherently inequitable or unjust. Nor do we posit that the scenarios explored here are inherently equitable or just. Instead, this protocol is designed to shed light on trade-offs and co-benefits in the context of a set of justice considerations that have seen limited research to date. Providing thematic structure in this context, the expert elicitation yielded broad consensus that meeting development needs, addressing regional inequities and ensuring the protection of natural systems were priority areas needing stronger representation within IAMs, which we prioritize in this effort (ibid.). Moreover, experts stressed the importance of transparency and clarity in communicating how justice considerations shape scenario assumptions and results, which we initiate through the open peer review of this protocol (ibid.).

Conceptually, we situate the scenario set we examine in the broader multi-disciplinary justice literature through recent research describing and interpreting interregional, intergenerational, and interspecies justice as crucial dimensions of Earth System Justice that ought to feature in contemporary integrated assessment modelling efforts (Gupta et al. 2023). Interregional justice recognizes the differentiated historical responsibilities, capacities, needs and vulnerabilities across and within regions, advocating fairer distributions of climate mitigation efforts and development outcomes. Intergenerational justice emphasizes obligations to future generations, for example

¹ We refer to the broader set of equity, fairness and justice considerations in short as ‘justice considerations’ in the remainder of this protocol.

through constraints on the depletion of resources and expected climate overshoot impacts and management responsibilities. Interspecies justice advocates stewardship that actively safeguards non-human species and ecosystems within mitigation pathways. Complementing this conceptual framing is an understanding that meeting development needs must extend beyond GDP. Instead of relying only on income-based poverty measures, we use the multidimensional Decent Living Standards (DLS) framework (Rao and Min 2018), and apply an approach that combines this framework with studies of household energy access and energy poverty (Chakravarty and Tavoni 2013; Dagnachew et al. 2018; Pachauri et al. 2021). This helps us estimate national minimum energy needs—known as Decent Living Energy (DLE) thresholds—which account for both energy use and how it is provided (Rao et al. 2019; Millward-Hopkins et al. 2020; Kikstra et al. 2021; Kikstra et al. 2025).

This protocol proposes a set of scenarios that systematically examine and interact the following elements: i) stricter sustainability constraints on biomass use and geological carbon storage, including biodiversity restoration targets, ii) universal DLS and substantial energy consumption and access inequality reduction, and iii) an effort-sharing mechanism alongside considerations of historical responsibility. In examining their interactions, we introduce new pathways that explore trade-offs and co-benefits across a set of underrepresented considerations in the IAM literature. The following three primary research questions are explored, under the overarching ambition to meet the Paris Agreement long-term temperature goal:

1. What are the implications of meeting minimum energy needs, defined as achieving DLS for all, for meeting global and regional climate mitigation targets?
2. What are the implications of introducing regional effort-sharing, for meeting global and regional climate mitigation targets?
3. What are the implications of the interaction between meeting minimum needs and effort-sharing, for meeting global and regional climate mitigation targets?

The appendix of this protocol documents all stakeholder interactions that informed the development of the proposed scenario set, alongside further literature and theory discussions underpinning the main assumptions.

2. Overview

The design of the scenario set follows the research questions outlined in the introduction. We structure the elements examined along two primary axes: Decent Living Standards (DLS) and Effort Sharing (ES), both of which limit biomass use and geological carbon storage, which we discuss in the subsequent section (see Figure 1). The scenario set is based on selected Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) that describe varying social, economic, and political developments (O'Neill et al. 2017) and the most recent updates to the participating IAM assumptions in the wake of CMIP7 model intercomparison (Van Vuuren et al. 2026). We introduce this briefly here, before describing the implementation approach and conceptual basis in further detail in the subsequent sections.

Figure 1 Scenario matrix for a set of Research Questions (RQ) combining Decent Living Standards (DLS) and Effort Sharing (ES) dimensions, including Minimum needs (MN) and Reduced inequality (RI) aspects. An asterisk (*) next to SSP indicates slight deviations from default model-specific SSP assumptions, particularly regarding biomass use and geological storage constraints, as well as regional energy and GDP levels.

RQ1: What are the implications of meeting minimum energy needs, defined as achieving DLS for all, for meeting global and regional climate mitigation targets?

The [MN, MN-RI1, MN-RI2] scenario set addresses Research Question 1. MN introduces minimum needs thresholds consistent with DLS provisioning. The two RI variants add a further constraint as an upper bound on per capita final energy demand, which compresses the distribution from above. RI1 and RI2 differ in the stringency of this bound, with RI2 the more restrictive of the two. This is not a prescription of individual lifestyles, nor a ceiling enforced on personal consumption choices. Rather, the RI variants define, at the national aggregate level, a consumption corridor bounded from below by DLS minima and from above by a per capita energy threshold. The mechanisms through which such distributional shifts might be realized, whether fiscal, regulatory, infrastructural, or behavioral, remain outside the scope of the scenario design and would require complementary analysis. All scenarios in the DLS stream run under the SSP2 narrative, which represents moderate progress on development and environmental objectives.

RQ2: What are the implications of introducing regional effort-sharing, for meeting global and regional climate mitigation targets?

Along the ES axis, the [ES1] scenario is designed to answer Research Question 2, exploring how the introduction of international cooperation through financial transfers for climate and development alongside considerations of historical responsibility modify transformation pathways for meeting climate targets. This is conducted within the SSP1 scenario narrative, reflecting 'Taking the Green Road' where the world shifts toward sustainability, with reduced inequality and global cooperation.

RQ3: What are the implications of the interaction between meeting minimum needs and effort-sharing, for meeting global and regional climate mitigation targets?

The interactions between the DLS and ES axes [MN-ES1, MN+RI2-ES1] are designed to answer Research Question 3, exploring the co-benefits and trade-offs of both meeting minimum needs and addressing historical responsibilities through effort sharing and international cooperation. This is conducted within the SSP1 scenario narrative, reflecting a strongly cooperative and progressive global pathway for meeting climate targets.

3. Key parameters

This table serves as a reference for the key parameters discussed in the scenario protocol. The parameter settings and brief rationale described here are supplemented by theoretical and practical reasoning in subsequent sections and appendices.

Table 1 - Summary of key parameters

Parameter	Setting	Brief Rationale
Socio-economic Pathways	SSP1 and SSP2	SSP2 is widely used, allowing for comparability with literature, and a good contrast between DLS scenarios vs. extending historical trends. For ES stream, SSP1 is chosen as a future in which international cooperation on climate mitigation is strengthened.
Full-century Carbon Budget	800 Gt CO ₂ (2020-2100).	Consistent with a likely 2°C carbon budget (with at least 67% likelihood) which is found to be technically feasible in all participating IAMs, enabling exploration of diverse justice considerations (Forster et al. 2026).
First Model Timestep	2030	We consider model timestep 2030, representative of 2026-2030 inclusive, as the appropriate starting point.
Biodiversity	Align with Leclère et al. (2020a), restoring the global Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) back to 1990s or earlier levels, with regional convergence where possible.	Partially addresses interspecies justice concerns and biodiversity impacts of large-scale biomass deployment.
Biomass Sustainability Constraints	Biomass limit of 100 EJ/year ±10% (preferred) or fallback of 130 EJ/year ±20%; assessment of regional land-use impacts recommended.	Recognizes strong links between biomass use and biodiversity loss (Gupta et al. 2023; Creutzig et al. 2015)
Geological CO ₂ Storage	Global storage limit of 1,460 Gt CO ₂ ; ≤25% of this (365 Gt CO ₂) used by 2100 (±20%).	Incorporates regionally informed risks of geological storage (e.g., leakage, ecosystem disruption) and avoids over-reliance on this option (Koornneef et al. 2012; Gidden et al. 2025); full 1,460 Gt would theoretically cover ~300 years total from now, but the protocol intentionally leaves ~75% unused as a precautionary buffer
DLS Achievement	Universal DLS by 2040; buildout starting from 2026 (with buildout present in the first model year after 2025). <i>Note: if there are (model) feasibility issues in implementing this ambitious timeframe, these will be dealt with individually.</i>	Mirrors the period of past international development goals (e.g., MDGs, SDGs) of around 15 years, providing a clear time horizon for infrastructure expansion. In the choice for this timeframe, there is a tradeoff between satisfying needs and reducing harm as soon as possible and scenario plausibility with near-term trends.
DLS Scenario Variants	MN: minimum DLS thresholds. MN+R11: uplift + limit high energy consumption. MN+R12: uplift + stronger living standard convergence.	Captures multiple justice dimensions (basic needs, reducing inequality, convergence in living standards between regions), reflecting energy needs associated with social and sustainable development targets — without prescribing how these distributional outcomes are achieved or implying uniform lifestyle changes across individuals.
ES Allocation principle	Marker approach: equal cumulative per capita allocation from the year 1990 of all net GHGs excluding LULUCF and shipping. Variants encouraged.	Reflects an interpretation of the ‘Common But Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities’ (CBDR&RC) principle anchored to the year 1990, while providing flexibility for alternative (principles-first) approaches and specifications.
ES International Cooperation	From at least 100 billion USD to a maximum of 1% of global GDP (PPP) as annual climate and development finance transfer volumes, converted into a physical cap (Gt CO₂/yr) via each model's shadow price on covered emissions.	Reflects a floor and an upper threshold on international cooperation, drawing on recent work (Bauer et al. 2020). 1% of global GDP in 2024 was approx. 2 trillion PPP international \$.

4. Implementation

The scenario set allows for model-specific implementations, guided by a common framework to maintain comparability across the ensemble. We describe this framework below, with more detailed documentation and the underlying theoretical and practical rationale provided in the appendices.

Climate specifications

From early investigations within the ScenarioMIP-CMIP7 project with an updated climate emulator and emissions pathways harmonized to the latest available historical emissions data, we learn that a budget of 800 Gt CO₂ (2020-2100) generally features end-of-century temperatures of well-below 2°C, while peak temperatures tend to stay below 2°C with at least 67% likelihood.

Socioeconomic specifications

SSP2 is chosen as the main setting for the DLS axis to allow for assessing what the implications of providing DLS are compared to a reference mitigation scenario with middle-of-the-road characteristics (in contrast with SSP1, which endogenously embeds improved development trajectories and reduced inequality compared to historical trends in its narrative). We transition from SSP2 to SSP1 for the ES axis (and the interactions) to align the effort-sharing framework with the equity-oriented socioeconomic assumptions embedded within the SSP1 narrative (O'Neill et al. 2017).

Biodiversity considerations

In line with conceptual framing and expert-elicited areas of focus, we recommend incorporating biodiversity considerations across all scenarios outlined in this protocol. These considerations should be applied consistently across scenarios, even if doing so requires deviations from default model-specific SSP configurations. We propose two ways to implement this consideration:

- (1) Using the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII):

If a model can estimate and report the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII), we propose aligning it with the assumptions and BII trajectories outlined in an ambitious Integrated Action Portfolio (IAP) scenario. This scenario, developed using several key IAMs in the study by Leclère et al. (2020), includes major efforts to reverse biodiversity loss. It reflects the goal of “bending the curve” – restoring global biodiversity to levels seen at least around 1990 or earlier depending on the model, which may begin at different levels, with regional convergence where possible.

- (2) Applying a primary energy biomass constraint:

Previous studies have identified a correlation between assumed biomass production levels and potential biodiversity trade-offs (Hanssen et al. 2022; Hof et al. 2018). Building on this evidence, we recommend that models unable to directly constrain the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) instead apply a constraint on primary biomass energy production.

Where feasible, models should apply the more stringent biomass production threshold of **100 EJ/year** (Creutzig et al. 2015). If this is not attainable, a relaxed threshold of **130 EJ/year ±20%** may be used, as it aligns with the U.N. Convention on Biological Diversity’s goal of protecting one-third of global land area (Frank et al. 2021) and remains broadly consistent with sustainable biomass estimates from other studies. However, applying a global constraint alone may overlook region-specific land-use pressures. *Therefore, we recommend that modelling teams also assess how the global biomass constraint affects regional land-use patterns during the scenario vetting process.*

Modelling teams may use a variety of levers to meet these BII or biomass constraints. Each team should document its chosen approach and apply it consistently across all scenario variants. Trade-offs between biodiversity conservation and food security are well recognized (Leclère et al., 2020). Two methods representing the biodiversity considerations proposed in this protocol can have different implications for food security (Appendix A1). *We recommend that modelling teams assess the food security implications by reporting relevant food security indicators (e.g. FAO 2025) derived from their model outputs. Indicator selection is at the discretion of each modelling team.*

Geological carbon storage

Geological storage of CO₂ poses potential environmental risks, including leakage from pipelines and injection wells (Koornneef et al. 2012; Gidden et al. 2025) that could disrupt local ecosystems and contaminate groundwater, thus leading to adverse effects on nature and biodiversity. These concerns, along with the need to avoid sensitive or protected areas, limit the global potential for geological storage. Considering these risks, we propose a global usage limit of **365 Gt CO₂ ±20%** to 2100 for geological storage, explicitly capped at 25% of the 1,460 Gt CO₂ global potential identified by Gidden et al (2025). The remaining ~75% is intentionally left unused as a buffer to reflect uncertainty and risk.

DLS scenarios design

Past studies have shown that ensuring universal access to key energy services may lead to increased energy demand and associated emissions, depending on the climate policy and how equally resources are distributed (Huo et al. 2023; Kikstra et al. 2021; Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, van Vuuren, et al. 2025; McElroy and O'Neill 2025; Millward-Hopkins and Oswald 2023; Rammelt et al. 2023; Schlesier et al. 2024). Therefore, we propose three variants within the DLS axis to explore a range of different interpretations of providing DLS for all while reducing inequality. These variants contribute to RQ1 when considered independently and in reference to the base SSP2 scenario, and RQ3 when interacted with the ES axis scenarios.

The first variant, “Minimum Needs” (MN), assumes additional energy and service provision sufficient to ensure that all individuals currently below the Decent Living Standards (DLS) are brought up to these minimum thresholds. Modelling teams first create a reference mitigation scenario with a carbon budget of 800 Gt CO₂. Using the DESIRE model (Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, van Vuuren, et al. 2025) energy gaps are calculated. Subsequently, teams are informed how much additional energy and service provisioning is required in each sector (Buildings, Transport, Industry) for operational energy and new infrastructure. With this information, new “MN” scenarios are created ensuring societal minimum energy and service provisioning by 2040.

The second variant, “Minimum Needs + Reduced Inequality 1” (MN+RI1), preserves this universal uplift while also assuming that disproportionately high per capita energy consumption will be avoided. The third variant, “Minimum Needs + Reduced Inequality 2” (MN+RI2), similarly raises everyone above the DLS threshold but incorporates a stronger convergence in living standards, with a larger share of affluent populations transitioning to lower carbon lifestyles. Both MN+RI1 and MN+RI2 achieved this additional inequality reduction at the same time as the minimum needs provisioning. The levels of inequality reduction modelled in these scenarios are the outcome of a series of workshops (Appendix A4) and the rationale and details behind all assumptions are explained in more detail in Appendix A2. Together, MN+RI1 and MN+RI2 aim to reflect a range of expressed inequality preferences, while noting that the specific values used here are one possible interpretation of the available literature.

These scenario variations do not assume or prescribe specific policy instruments to achieve the proposed final energy reductions of the wealthy but explore a quantitative range consistent with different aggregate mean living standards. As in previous studies (Millward-Hopkins and Oswald 2021, 2023), the goal is to explore the implications of such final energy demand increases and reductions for climate targets, and in our setup, for transformations in the energy system in line with explicitly assumed climate mitigation policies. To systematically examine these effects, we ask teams to apply the same carbon prices used in the SSP2 reference mitigation scenario when running the different DLS configurations, as a proxy for equal mitigation effort. One crucial outcome of this exercise is an estimate of emissions and climate implications (e.g. peak global surface temperature) that can be allocated to providing minimum needs in a future that implements ambitious climate policy. An optional variant may be run that fixes the carbon budget (instead of the carbon price) to proxy equal climate outcomes (instead of equal mitigation effort), from which we instead learn different regional efforts with and without minimum needs achievement. Finally, an optional set can be run using SSP1 for comparison with the ES scenario stream as noted in our *Optional scenarios* section.

ES scenarios design

Fairness considerations have been central to international climate mitigation discourse since the early multilateral deliberations (Grubb 1995). While the Paris Agreement's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) framework replaces the differentiated and prescriptive targets under the Kyoto Protocol, it emphasizes temperature limits (well below 2°C, aiming for 1.5°C) alongside considerations of a range of principles including 'common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities' (CBDR&RC). Considerations of fairness have long been linked to the notion of a remaining carbon budget for staying below a probabilistic temperature limit (R. K. Pachauri 2010). Recent research underscores that many countries have exceeded their fair share of such a budget, consequently accruing disproportionate responsibility for climate overshoot (Li et al. 2025; Pelz, Ganti, Lamboll, et al. 2025; Dekker et al. 2025). The effort sharing (ES) axis scenario variants explicitly address this, integrating regional emissions constraints that reflect differentiated responsibility considerations with a flexible international climate and development finance cooperation mechanism to address regional overshoot responsibility. The source scenarios we examine comprise scenarios without DLS considerations (ES1) and interactions with DLS variants (MN-ES1 and MN-RI2-ES1). These scenarios address RQ 2 when considered independently and in reference to the base SSP1 scenario, and RQ 3 when interacted with the DLS axis variants.

To implement these scenarios, we distinguish **covered emissions** — subject to explicit fairness considerations and flexible effort sharing — from **excluded emissions**, which are managed globally on a least-cost basis without explicit fairness considerations. For this intercomparison, covered emissions encompass cumulative net Kyoto gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) excluding LULUCF, aggregated to CO₂-equivalent using GWP-100 (AR6). "Cumulative" indicates that the fairness criterion is applied to each region's total over the full budget horizon rather than to annual emissions, so regions retain flexibility over the timing of their emissions. Each region receives a cumulative fair-share budget, and regions may trade certificates against these budgets. Excluded emissions — here, LULUCF CO₂ — are not allocated to regions; they are driven by a uniform global carbon price applied on a least-cost basis. LULUCF is excluded because land-sector fluxes are difficult to attribute to individual regions in a fairness-meaningful way and behave differently from energy-system emissions; including them in a per-capita allocation would distort the fairness criterion (see Appendix A3). International shipping is treated as a separate case: it is neither allocated nor subject to the global price, but held fixed at its

source-scenario trajectory, as these emissions cannot be attributed to any single region. Teams will refer to code translating native IAMC reporting variables into regional cumulative *covered* emissions constraints from the first native model period through to the model horizon (<https://github.com/setupelz/fair-shares>). The marker approach is defined as an equal cumulative per capita allocation from the year 1990 (see A3 for normative considerations underlying this selection). Other variants will be actively pursued and are encouraged, and should reflect a principles-first approach (Rajamani et al. 2021; Dooley et al. 2021; Pelz, Ganti, Pachauri, et al. 2025). Teams must ensure native model regions respect cumulative *covered* emissions constraints in their model frameworks, avoiding any overdrafts by the end of the model horizon but without upper limits on remaining allocations.

Limited transfers of climate and development finance are considered, with an annual floor of 100 B USD and a ceiling of 1% of global GDP (PPP), following prior explorations by Bauer et al. (2020). In practice, the GDP-share ceiling is translated into an annual physical (Gt CO₂/yr) cap on international cooperation by dividing the share of global GDP by each model's shadow price on *covered* emissions. Because introducing this physical cap raises domestic prices in debtor regions and lowers them in creditor regions, the monetary volume implied by the resulting equilibrium is always below the original GDP share used to define the cap, reflecting an 'upper bound property' that allows teams to iterate upward from a low starting share (0.05% of global GDP) until the model returns a feasible solution. Cross-model variance in the minimum feasible cooperation share is an intended feature of the experiment and should be reported.

Scenarios checklist

Scenarios are organized by research question (RQ1: DLS stream; RQ2: ES stream; RQ3: combined stream). Scenario names encode the SSP, budget, and policy design features (DLS and/or ES, including variants). “ES Transfers” indicates the level of effort-sharing transfers applied (none, limited, full). Unless otherwise noted, all scenarios including an effort-sharing (ES) component use the primary marker allocation year of 1990. Teams that are unable to implement 1990 may instead submit scenarios using allocation year 2015. In such cases, the allocation year must be explicitly reported alongside the scenario name in all submissions and outputs.

Table 2 - Overview of the proposed and optional scenarios

Scenario Name	Budget	Carbon price	SSP	DLS	DLS variant	ES	ES Transfers
Reference:							
_SSP1_800f_	800		1	no	no	no	no
_SSP2_800f_	800		2	no	no	no	no
DLS stream (RQ1):							
_SSP2_dls1	?	_SSP2_800f_	2	yes	MN	no	no
_SSP2_dls2	?	_SSP2_800f_	2	yes	MN+R11	no	no
_SSP2_dls3	?	_SSP2_800f_	2	yes	MN+R12	no	no
ES stream (RQ2):							
_SSP1_800f_es1	800		1	no	no	yes	limited
Combined stream (RQ3):							
_SSP1_800f_dls1_es1	800		1	yes	MN	yes	limited
Optional							
_SSP2_800f_dls1	800		2	yes	MN	no	no
_SSP2_800f_dls2	800		2	yes	MN+R11	no	no
_SSP2_800f_dls3	800		2	yes	MN+R12	no	no
_SSP1_800f_dls3_es1	800		1	yes	MN+R12	yes	limited
_SSP1_800f_dls2_es1	800		1	yes	MN+R11	yes	limited
_SSP1_800f_es2	800		1	no	no	yes	no
_SSP1_800f_dls1_es2	800		1	yes	MN	yes	no
_SSP1_800f_dls1_es3	800		1	yes	MN	yes	full
_SSP1_800f_dls2_es2	800		1	yes	MN+R11	yes	no
_SSP1_800f_dls2_es3	800		1	yes	MN+R11	yes	full
_SSP1_800f_dls3_es2	800		1	yes	MN+R12	yes	no
_SSP1_800f_dls3_es3	800		1	yes	MN+R12	yes	full

5. Submission

All scenarios will be centrally submitted and accessible in the [justMIP scenario explorer](#) hosted by IIASA. This is an open scenario explorer with iterative releases to the public as research questions are resolved. Before submission, scenario results must be checked to comply with all features in Table 1. All submissions will undergo comprehensive vetting, and results will be reviewed with the respective modeling teams.

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Appendix

A1 – Biodiversity, biomass and food security

Biodiversity restoration is a crucial aspect of interspecies and intergenerational justice (Gupta et al. 2023). Returning land to nature is measured in different ways in the literature (Burgess et al. 2024). Goals and targets often reflect land-share constraints, for example, conserving 30% of all land (target 3 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework); conserving 50% of all land (“Half Earth” from EO Wilson (2016)); conserving 50-60% of all land (Rockström et al. 2023). In this protocol we apply the biodiversity intactness indicator (BII) to center biodiversity and include an optional global biomass energy limit as a proxy, keeping in mind the various participating model capabilities. Estimated BII in 2020 is illustrated in Figure A1.

Figure A1. Biodiversity intactness index (BII) in 2020 and examples in (A) Northeast America, (B) Amazon, (C) Mekong Delta, (D) Eastern Australia, (E) Northeast China, (F) Nile Delta in Egypt, (G) Southern Africa, and (H) Western Europe. Green represents intact ecosystems and red indicates ecosystems with high human intervention. Figure from Nguyen et al. (2025) under CC BY-NC-ND 4.0.

Biodiversity targets, particularly at higher ambition levels, can interact with food systems in complex ways. On the one hand, ambitious biodiversity targets may compromise food security, particularly in low-income regions (Mehrabi et al. 2018; Henry et al. 2022), by reducing agricultural land, lowering food production and availability, and increasing farm-gate prices. On the other hand, implementing biodiversity constraints through limits on biomass production may alleviate food security risks, as large-scale deployment of Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) can threaten food security in absence of redistributive policy measures by intensifying land competition and raising food prices (Hasegawa et al. 2020; Fuhrman et al. 2020).

To systematically assess these trade-offs, we recommend participating modeling teams to adopt the FAO's analytical framework (FAO 2025b), which defines the food security across four key dimensions: availability, access, stability, and utilization. FAOSTAT also provides a suite of food security indicators, among which the SDG Indicator 2.1.1 on the prevalence of undernourishment has been used in the integrated assessment modeling community to assess hunger risk and food security (Hasegawa et al. 2019). Drawing on these measures and their analogues in model implementations, we will work with modelling teams to review the implications of biodiversity constraints in their model frameworks and consider guardrails such as the biomass energy constraint to ensure that food security is not threatened.

A2 – Decent Living Standards

Ensuring minimum needs satisfaction

While existing income-based measures remain useful for assessing poverty through the concept of a ‘social floor,’ there is a growing recognition of the need to move beyond absolute poverty lines (Edward 2006). Ideally, studies should recognize and incorporate the multidimensionality of human development itself (Alkire 2002), as well as the multitude of potential means to achieve wellbeing – noting that it is these means, or wellbeing satisfiers, that determine the nature of environment-poverty interactions. Building on the philosophical frameworks that emphasize access to a Decent Living Standard (DLS) as one possible, pragmatic way towards a more comprehensive and just approach (Caney 2009; Rao and Min 2018), there have been growing efforts to operationalize DLS in the context of energy access through quantifying minimum energy requirements for providing DLS, also known as the concept of Decent Living Energy (Rao and Baer 2012; Rao et al. 2019; Millward-Hopkins et al. 2020; Kikstra et al. 2021; Millward-Hopkins and Oswald 2023; Kikstra et al. 2025). One core assumption underlying this line of research is that it aims to define a universal level of services required for a decent living standard constituent (e.g., thermal comfort heating or cooling standards). Nonetheless, it importantly recognizes that the energy needs associated to those service levels are context-specific, and have been quantified around the world (Rao and Baer 2012; Rao et al. 2019; Millward-Hopkins et al. 2020; Kikstra et al. 2021; Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, Van Vuuren, et al. 2025).

Building on this strand of literature, we use energy as the modelling entry-point for integrating human development in scenarios. We operationalize Decent Living Standards (DLS) through the energy required to ensure access to DLS, including essential services such as transport, space and water heating, health care, appliances, sanitation, shelter, space cooling, education, nutrition, clothing, and water (Rao and Baer 2012; Rao and Min 2018; Kikstra et al. 2021; Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, Van Vuuren, et al. 2025). This should be understood as one, but not the only theoretically possible, quantification entry-point for DLS, where quantifications for decent living materials (Vélez-Henao and Pauliuk 2023; Streeck et al. 2025) and other resources (Vélez-Henao et al. 2026) are also available. However, these resources have not yet been linked to IAM scenarios as it has been done for energy (Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, Van Vuuren, et al. 2025). For each service, a minimum threshold is defined, below which a decent living standard may not be materially satisfied. This reflects the incorporation of a sufficientarian perspective (Scheifinger et al. 2026), or a *floor*, which emphasizes that everyone should attain *at least* (it may be more than this floor) a certain threshold of wellbeing, along with the associated required resources.

Due to the lack of detailed, country-specific data on how access to essential services and their respective resource consumption footprints are distributed within populations, existing studies often need to rely on assumptions about the distributional shape of service access. Given this limited data, (Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, Van Vuuren, et al. 2025) argue for a parsimonious approach which assumes that the energy consumption of a particular set of services follows a log-normal distribution (which is shown to perform better than other distributions for residential energy consumption data). We follow this approach, combining the mean energy consumption level and the estimated energy Gini coefficient in each country, to estimate how consumption is spread across the population. This, in turn, makes it possible to quantify the additional energy requirements needed to lift all individuals up to the level of resource consumption

level associated with DLS (those consuming more than this minimum energy requirement are not affected in this calculation). We call this the energy needs gap.

The core logic and implications of these assumptions are illustrated in Figure A2, where the right panel presents the first proposed Decent Living Standards (DLS) variant: the Minimum Needs (MN) scenario.

Figure A2 Illustration of Minimum Needs (MN) scenario by showing an illustrative (within-country, within-sector) energy use distribution from low, with the height representing the share of the population living at that level of energy per capita use. Left panel: Reference scenario. Right panel: implied energy distribution in the Minimum Needs (MN) scenario.

Estimates of the additional energy requirements can vary significantly across different temperature targets and socio-economic assumptions (Millward-Hopkins et al. 2020; Kikstra et al. 2021; Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, Van Vuuren, et al. 2025). These differences stem from varying assumptions about technological advancements, energy efficiency improvements, and service distribution across populations. Thus, any estimation of the global DLS energy requirements remains inherently context and scenario dependent. To deal with these context and scenario specificities, in this protocol, we propose the use of the DESIRE model to scale DLS energy requirements over time, for different countries, across scenarios (Kikstra, Daioglou, Min, Sferra, Soergel, Kriegler, Lee, Mastrucci, Pachauri, Rao, Rauner, Van Vuuren, et al. 2025). The evolution of energy needs gaps should therefore reflect the modelling assumptions made in each specific scenario implementation.

Reducing inequality by curbing high consumption

A growing body of literature argues that poverty eradication is less constrained by a global shortage of resources and more by systematic inefficiencies in providing the services and goods people need. Studies increasingly show how large global inequalities are (Oswald et al. 2020) and how inequality and high consumption, particularly in the Global North, is related to environmental degradation and climate damages (Bruckner et al. 2022; Kikstra et al. 2021; Millward-Hopkins et al. 2020; Rao et al. 2019; Schlesier et al. 2024; Streeck et al. 2025; Schöngart et al. 2025; Vélez-Henao and Pauliuk 2023). These analyses highlight that without addressing inequalities in resource distribution, efforts to alleviate poverty risk driving up resource demands, thereby conflicting with climate and environmental goals. While extensive literature critiques excessive income, consumption, and living standards for their negative environmental and social impacts, particularly when concentrated among a small segment of the population, there remains limited dedicated research and data specifically on the super-rich (Otto et al. 2019). Moreover, there is no clear consensus on quantitative thresholds defining an upper bound on living standards that would characterize such excess in elements such as travel frequency or living space per person, despite growing interest in alternative consumption

patterns driven by varying assumptions on reduced income inequality (Pauliuk 2024; Sampedro et al. 2024).

Despite differences in cultural and socio-economic contexts, there is a broad societal agreement that current levels of inequality are unfair. For example, one study (Kiatpongsan and Norton 2014) demonstrated through a survey across 40 countries that people consistently favor limiting income disparities, expressed as preferred ratios between CEO pay and that of unskilled workers, regardless of cultural or economic background. This widespread preference for capping excessive inequality suggests that similar principles could be extended to other domains of resource distribution, including energy use, as for example explored by (Millward-Hopkins and Oswald 2021). While there are many studies on (mis)perceived inequality (e.g., Gimpelson and Treisman 2018) and laboratory experiments (e.g., Starmans et al. 2017; Kamas and Preston 2012), the survey results used here are one of the few peer-reviewed studies that quantify, in many countries around the world, what inequality preferences people hold for the relationship between lower earners and higher earners.

At the same time, studies have pointed out that energy demand reductions can come with many benefits, among which a high mitigation potential, health benefits through better air quality, active mobility and dietary shifts, increased energy access and affordability, reduced material consumption, and higher energy security (Creutzig et al. 2018, 2022; Bento et al. 2024; Grubler et al. 2018; Sugiyama et al. 2024). While options to avoid (additional) service demand show large potential, they are often neglected in climate policies (Brad et al. 2025). Similarly, limitarian approaches to distributive justice focusing on limiting excessive consumption are scarce in the climate mitigation scenario literature (Zimm et al. 2024) despite the potential of reduced inequality (Büchs et al. 2023; Millward-Hopkins and Oswald 2023) and luxury-focused taxation (Oswald et al. 2023).

Figure A3 Illustration of Minimum Needs with Reductions in Inequality (MN+RI) scenarios by showing an illustrative (within-country, within-sector) energy use distribution, going from the low to high energy use per capita, with the height representing the share of the population living at that level of energy per capita use. Left panel: Reference scenario. Right panel: implied energy distribution in the Minimum Needs with Reductions in Inequality (MN+RI) variants. The dot in the right panel represents the mean of the distribution. The MN part always increases the mean, while the RI part reduces the mean energy use.

In this context, also noting that the MN scenario increases aggregate energy demand, it becomes relevant to investigate how a more equal distribution of service consumption, specifically by reducing the ratio between the minimum decent living standard (DLS) level and the maximum consumption levels for a given service, could affect global final energy demand and, in turn, influence mitigation outcomes and mitigation strategies (Figure A3). In our exercise, we primarily depart from the perspective of exploring a range of ‘ideal’ or ‘preferred’ levels of inequality, which we then link to

living standards, instead of departing from an approach that derives a maximum level of energy inequality under a scenario that also provides minimum needs as done for instance in (Jaccard et al. 2021) for the EU, and (Betts-Davies et al. 2025) for the UK. This decision was the outcome of a series of workshops among experts in the project consortium (Appendix A4).

Building on these insights, we introduce two additional scenario variants that combine the concept of Minimum Needs with Reductions in Inequality (MN+RI1 and MN+RI2) through assumptions about overall decreases in final energy demand. These two variants explore different magnitudes of inequality reduction and aggregate service demand, providing a broader perspective on potential outcomes. In this protocol, we remain agnostic about the specific policy measures or mechanisms through which such reductions could be achieved. Our focus lies on the implications of achieving a more equitable distribution on service consumption, rather than prescribing any particular means of doing so.

Minimum needs variant implementation

The “minimum needs” variant is labelled MN. Based on the submitted Reference scenarios, we (a) downscale the final energy sectors to get country-level energy demand by sector, (b) run DESIRE to get the energy needs gap, and (c) calculate multiplication factors (MFs) to meet this gap by the year 2040, as shown in Figure A4. These MFs are then used to create the scenario MN variant. These MFs are derived from the final energy projected by the IAM, but crucially account for improvements in service provisioning efficiency – recognizing that the energy required to meet DLS may decline over time, especially in the presence of ambitious climate policies (Kikstra et al. 2025). The MFs are therefore rather reflecting relative increases in services. Model implementations of these MFs will differ, but their implementation should reflect these changes in (mean) services as faithfully as possible.

Figure A4: Overview of technical DLS implementation.

We set 2040 as the year of DLS achievement, giving an ambitious 15 years for the provisioning of infrastructure, which is equally long as was given between the publication and target of the Millennium

Development Goals, as well as the Sustainable Development Goals. In our modelling, the default *rate* of closing decent living gaps will be kept constant, starting the buildout of new DLS-provisioning infrastructure directly after 2025 (thus, in 2026, or the first following model year), until 2040. This is expected to result in a (near) linear increase of additional (i.e., relative to the reference mitigation scenario) energy demand from 2025 until 2040. This includes energy for constructing commensurate new infrastructure to support expanding DLS access. To cope with feasibility challenges due to the rise of energy demand, however, each modelling team can implement a different rate of DLS gaps closure in the transition period 2025-2040. After 2040, full DLS infrastructure is already built, and the remaining additional energy is based only on “contemporary energy” gaps in the underlying reference scenario (i.e., operational energy and energy for replacing infrastructure). This also means that in regions that require significant new infrastructure (industrial) energy demand increases substantially until 2040 and may drop in the first model timestep post-2040.

In increasing energy use in the scenarios using the multiplication factors, modelling teams should, where they can, ensure that the additional energy demand is fulfilled with clean energy, for instance avoiding the use of traditional biomass in non-clean cookstoves (which comes with negative health impacts through air pollution). Modelling teams may implement this differently, as change in services, useful energy, or final energy, depending on what best fits their model.

Modelling teams are also encouraged to find model-specific implementation routes for adjusting GDP alongside changes in energy use (& living standards). The lack of clarity in empirical literature on the (structural) economic effects of ambitious poverty eradication to the level of Decent Living Standards prevents us from prescribing a common approach. Not only is there limited research on this, but it is also clear that any such interventions have different effects depending on the context such as the sectoral policies, the level of commodification of service provisioning (vs. providing them as free or subsidized goods and services). With energy here being the effective modelling entry point, modelling teams are similarly encouraged to scale other resource demands in line with the sector increases in energy use, such as material or water resource demand, where possible.

Finally, despite the DLS levels being chosen based on best available scientific evidence of basic human needs (e.g. nutrition) or on intuitive thresholds of minimum access to some essential services (e.g. availability of appliances per household, or at least one mobile phone per capita), for many needs dimensions there is no clear minimum threshold that can be universally defined as “decent” (e.g. minimum travel distance, or housing floor space). This entails that other levels of (time-variant) services could possibly be used to define the translation of material Decent Living Standards to their energy requirements. For example, this could include recognizing that future systemic changes will entail that some services will become more prominent than others. We also note that, although we differentiate energy requirements to provide the same services across different countries based on social, climatic and infrastructural factors, we do not capture such heterogeneity within countries but rather treat each country as a whole.

Decent Living Standard thresholds

Transport

The DLS threshold for transport is defined on a country-specific basis following [Millward-Hopkins et al. \(2020\)](#). The threshold captures the travel passenger-kilometres (pkm) necessary to meet basic mobility needs — including access to employment, education, health care, and essential services — while accounting for:

- Population density;
- Settlement patterns (urban vs. rural distinctions);
- The need to correct for uninhabited land, which would otherwise inflate per-capita distance requirements.

In practice, the threshold represents the minimum motorised mobility that enables meaningful participation in society given a country's spatial structure, and it varies substantially across national contexts. The thresholds therefore range **from a minimum of 4903 km/cap/year (or ~13 km/cap/day)** in Singapore **to a maximum of 13900 km/cap/year (or ~38 km/cap/day)** in Eswatini. The median value, found for Azerbaijan, is 7400 km/cap/year (~20 km/cap/day).

Shelter

The DLS threshold for shelter requires durable, permanent housing for all individuals. The minimum floor space is defined as:

- 30 m² for a single-person household or households of up to three people;
- An additional 10 m² per person for each person above three in the household.

This specification reflects the minimum space standards necessary to avoid overcrowding and to support basic functions such as sleeping, cooking, sanitation, and study.

This entails floorspace thresholds that vary across different countries based on household sizes between 10 m²/cap (for Afghanistan, with an average of 8 people/household) and 14.7 m²/cap (for Finland, with an average of 2.1 ppl/hh). To avoid grandfathering current household-size structures into the future, we take the midpoint of the range, found for Poland at **12.4 m²/cap**, and apply it to all countries.

Other need dimensions

For other dimensions, such as nutrition, health care, education, thermal comfort, appliances, water, sanitation, and clothing, the minimum service levels are set based on existing literature on decent living standards, and they are reported in Table A1.

[Reducing inequality variant implementation](#)

The two “Minimum needs with reductions in inequality” scenarios are labelled MN+RI1 and MN+RI2. As in the initial MN variant, the implementation of these thresholds is assumed to be gradual, rather than immediate. Specifically, we assume a constant rate of inequality reduction in terms of energy demand changes starting from zero in 2025 to 2040, with the reduced levels of inequality being achieved by 2040 and maintained beyond.

Each modelling team will receive a new set of multiplication factors, which are always lower than those in the MN variant. These MFs are again derived from DESIRE, here as the combination of energy use increases to provide DLS and energy use decreases for reduced inequality. The MFs determine the necessary change in average per capita energy consumption. In high-consumption regions, these factors can fall below 1, if energy reductions to fall below an upper consumption limit are greater than the energy increase to lift above Minimum Needs. In such cases, both energy demand and, depending on each team's modelling choices, potentially GDP, can decline relative to the scenario without explicit DLS targets. Information will be provided about how much of the energy change is attributable to providing for minimum needs, versus how much comes from reducing inequality.

Setting upper limits in consumption distribution to examine scenarios of reduced inequality remains a debated and contentious issue. Following expert consultations, we adopted a combination of methods developed by Millward-Hopkins (2022) and Millward-Hopkins et al. (2021, 2023). Their approach uses findings from a global study on CEO-to-unskilled worker pay ratios (Kiatpongsan and Norton 2014) to set empirically motivated limits for reducing inequality. This study revealed how people in different countries perceive fair income differences. Millward-Hopkins and colleagues use these ratios to define the acceptable gap between the top 1% and the bottom 10% of consumers within a given service consumption distribution. The key assumption is that people's views on fair income inequality can be used to proxy and motivate what people see as fair inequality in material and energy consumption.

For two of the most important energy consumption dimensions, housing and mobility, we convert earning ratios into service ratios, more specifically into residential floor space per capita (m^2 per person) and passenger-kilometers (p-km). To do this, we draw on within-country survey data from high-income nations, where large segments of the population already exhibit very high consumption levels. This data helps us estimate the typical living standards associated with a theoretical CEO-level income, providing an empirically rooted basis for setting upper consumption limits.

Shelter: Floor Space Upper Thresholds

Starting Point: EU-SILC Data

The derivation begins with microdata from the European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) survey, which provides harmonised, country-level observations of floor space and household income across EU member states. These data allow the construction of empirical income–floor space distributions for each country in the sample.

Step 1: Identifying the Reference Income Point

For each country, the national minimum wage is used as an empirical proxy for the income of an unskilled worker. This serves as the anchor point (w_0) in the income distribution.

Two upper-bound income reference points are then computed by multiplying this anchor by the ratios reported in Kiatpongsan and Norton (2014):

- MN+RI1: $w_0 \times 20$ — reflecting the ratio that respondents considered a fair CEO-to-unskilled-worker pay differential (highest country-average value from the survey).
- MN+RI2: $w_0 \times 4.6$ — reflecting the ratio that respondents perceived as the actual fair differential (mean country-average value from the survey, entailing tighter convergence).

Step 2: Inferring Implied Floor Space Levels

Each multiplied income reference point is located within the country-level EU-SILC income–floor space distribution. The floor space value associated with that income level is then read off the empirical distribution, yielding an implied floor space ceiling for each country under each variant.

Step 3: Cross-Country Median

To arrive at a single, robust estimate for each variant, the median of the country-level implied floor space values is taken across all countries in the EU-SILC dataset. This yields:

- MN+RI1: **88 m^2** (median implied floor space ceiling) — corresponding to approximately the **90th percentile** of the EU population floor space distribution.

- MN+RI2: **53 m²** (median implied floor space ceiling) — corresponding to approximately the **67th percentile** of the EU population floor space distribution.

The percentile interpretation is important: it means that under MN+RI1, roughly 10% of the population would be asked to reduce floor space consumption, while under MN+RI2, approximately one-third of the population would be affected. Both variants preserve the DLS minimum floor for those currently below it.

Transport: Passenger Kilometre (pkm) Upper Thresholds

Data Availability and Choice of Reference Systems

Detailed micro-level data linking income to personal kilometres travelled (pkm) were available for only two countries: the United States and Japan. These two countries represent functionally opposite extremes of motorised transport system organisation:

- Japan represents a highly efficient, transit-oriented system with a relatively compressed pkm distribution;
- The United States represents a car-dependent, highly unequal system with a strongly right-skewed pkm distribution.

These two systems are therefore used as the two poles bounding the plausible range of transport consumption distributions globally.

Step 1: Identify Relevant Percentiles

For both countries, mobility levels corresponding to two percentiles of the pkm distribution are identified:

- **93th percentile → MN+RI1**
- **76th percentile → MN+RI2**

These percentiles are chosen to be consistent with the shelter percentiles, which emerged from the income-ratio approach applied to EU-SILC data. This proxies the idea that each Reduced Inequality variant entails a similar ambition level in reducing shelter and mobility consumption.

Step 2: Calculate Mobility Additional to the DLS Minimum

For each country and percentile, the additional mobility above the DLS level is calculated:

$$\Delta RI = Mobility_{upper\ percentile} - Mobility_{DLS}$$

This value represents the **mobility consumption corridor between the minimum mobility required for decent living standards and the upper bound**.

To avoid bias toward either a highly car-dependent or highly efficient transport system, the **mean ΔRI across the United States and Japan** is used, consisting of **25100 pkm/cap/year (~ 69 pkm/cap/day)** in RI1 and **7100 pkm/cap/year (~19 pkm/cap/day)** in RI2.

Step 3: Apply the Mobility Consumption Corridor Globally

The resulting average mobility consumption corridor is then added to each country's own DLS mobility requirement:

$$Mobility_{RI, country} = DLS_{country} + \overline{\Delta RI}$$

This approach preserves **country-specific baseline mobility needs**—which reflect differences in settlement structure, density, and travel requirements—while applying a common inequality constraint on mobility consumption.

Interpretation

Using the **mean difference between the United States and Japan** ensures that the resulting thresholds represent a **neutral midpoint between two contrasting mobility systems**. This avoids implicitly assuming either highly car-dependent or highly transit-oriented transport structures while maintaining a realistic bound on mobility consumption under the inequality scenarios.

Thresholds

The resulting upper thresholds are country-specific, and in the range of **~ 30 - 60 pkm/cap/day (~ 12500 – 21500 pkm/cap/year)** in the **RI2** variant (with higher values for low-density countries), and **~ 80 – 105 pkm/cap/day (~ 30000 – 39000 pkm/cap/year)** in **RI1**.

Upper thresholds for other consumption dimensionsOther consumption dimensions are included in our accounting, namely some additional residential energy for appliances and other uses, indirect energy consumption in the commercial sector, aviation mobility, and indirect energy for freight transport. The upper levels for these subsectors are calculated by observing current service consumption and setting an ambition level of reduction consistent with the passenger transport and living space thresholds in RI1 and RI2 variants. The details are reported in Table A2. Other services, such as data center deployment, were kept out of our analysis, due to uncertainty about future projections of energy consumption. It should be noted, however, that such increasing consumption could be categorized under the Industrial sector, for which we do not put any upper limit of consumption under the RI variants.

Handling of missing variables

When calculating the energy needs gap, some initial adjustments need to be made from the projections that IAMs provide, to ensure that the lognormal energy distributions are built solely on the energy that is required for minimum needs satisfaction and thus excluding the energy that can be considered beyond the minimum needs. For the building sector, this means first splitting residential from commercial energy and then selecting only the portion of commercial energy that is related to decent living service provisioning (in our calculations healthcare and education). Additionally, we assume that decent living energy should be fulfilled only with clean energy, and therefore we remove traditional biomass and coal from the accounting of residential energy. In the transport sector, we adjust by removing the final energy for aviation from the total transport energy, as this transport mode can be considered unnecessary to fulfill minimum needs. All adjustments require the reporting of the corresponding variables (final energy for commercial sector, final energy from traditional biomass and coal in the residential sector, final energy in the aviation sector). When such variables are missing in each IAM, we take the shares of energy (commercial out of total buildings, non-clean out of total residential, aviation out of total transportation) from another IAM that has share values near the average of all IAMs projections.

Another set of variables we draw from IAMs is related to the projection of service efficiency improvements in each of the three sectors. To model this, we estimate a service efficiency factor as a service variable (proxy for service provisioning) over final energy. For residential and commercial, we compute floor space or useful energy over final energy (in residential and commercial). For transportation, passenger-km or useful energy over final energy (in transportation). For industry,

production of cement and steel over final energy (in industry). When none of these service variables are reported in the IAM projections, we use a useful energy emulator originally developed for the NGFS project (Richters et al. 2022), which computes useful energy based on the fuel mix in final energy. This emulator estimates useful energy based on the current average final-to-useful energy conversion ratios of different fuels or carriers (e.g. in transport, electricity-based vehicles vs oil or gas-powered vehicles). This tool therefore captures the efficiency gains over time from aggregate fuel shifts in each sector but does not capture the energy efficiency improvements of single technologies within sectors (e.g. in transport, electric vehicles becoming more efficient). We recognize the limitation of this approach, which is however related to a more general lack of details on service variables inside IAMs, but we consider it as a reasonable first-order approximation to have an estimate of service efficiency improvements for DLS provisioning. Bilateral exchanges are being carried out with each IAM team, to better align the DLS calculations with the assumptions behind each IAM run and co-develop a methodology to cope with missing data.

Table A1 - Overview of key assumptions for the Minimum Needs scenario variants. The exact values of service and energy levels will possibly change during the model implementation, to better capture societal patterns of consumption.

DLS dimension	Decent living standards thresholds and proxies
Transport	Land-based travel needs vary in the range of 4903 – 13900 motorized passenger-kilometers per year per capita (median: 7400 km/cap/year for Azerbaijan), or 13-38 km/cap/day based on the nations' population density, as in Millward-Hopkins et al (2020), with public transport infrastructure relative to the p-km required based on current modal share estimates. Road network needs are calculated based on maintaining current infrastructures and a threshold of 1.5 km of paved road per square kilometer of arable land.
Space and water heating	Space heating up to 20 °C , and 30 l per capita per day of hot water.
Health care	Sufficient and accessible preventive and curative health care facilities. For energy calculations, this is proxied by high enough (government) expenditure (\$1024 per person per year) to sustain an average healthy life expectancy (HALE) of more than 65 years .
Appliances	One clean cookstove and fuel, mobile telephone, refrigerator, and television per household
Sanitation	Safely managed sanitation services for all.
Shelter	Durable permanent housing for all, with a minimum apartment size of 30 m² , increasing with 10 m² per person at household sizes above three, resulting in national minimum levels of 10–15 m ² /cap. We take the midpoint of the range, found for Poland at 12.4 m²/cap , and apply it to all countries.
Space cooling	Space cooling down to 26 °C .
Education	Adequate schooling with adequate facilities and staff. For energy calculations, this is proxied by high enough (government) expenditure (\$1400 and \$2900 per year per student for primary and lower secondary education, respectively) to sustain good completion rates.
Nutrition	Sufficiently healthy and nutritious diets, proxied by minimum dietary energy requirements (1653-2066 kcal/cap/day).
Clothing	Sufficient footwear and clothing. For energy calculations, this is proxied by weight and expenditures (footwear: 0.9 kg cap⁻¹ yr⁻¹ at \$15/kg, clothing: 1.3–2.5 kg cap⁻¹ yr⁻¹ at \$51 kg ⁻¹)
Water	Safely managed clean water supply of 65 l per capita per day .

Table A2 - Overview of key assumptions for the Reduced Inequality scenario variants. The exact values of service and energy levels will possibly change during the model implementation, to better capture societal patterns of consumption.

	Reduced Inequality 1 (RI1)	Reduced Inequality 2 (RI2)
Overall Rationale	More modest reduction in inequality; greater tolerance for high consumption levels	Stronger reduction in inequality
Residential Service Level	Floor space of 88 m²/cap (in line with inequality representing a 20:1 ratio between high and low earners)	Floor space of 53 m²/cap (in line with inequality representing a 4.6:1 ratio between high and low earners)
Residential Energy	Heating & cooling scale with m ² /cap; additional (discretionary) energy use of +20 GJ/cap/year for appliances, water, etc.	Heating & cooling scale with m ² /cap; additional (discretionary) energy use of +10 GJ/cap/year for appliances, water, etc.
Thermal Thresholds	No change (kept constant, with space heating up to 20°C and cooling down to 26°C)	No change (kept constant, with space heating up to 20°C and cooling down to 26°C)
Commercial Energy	Scales relative to residential energy using global commercial-to-residential energy ratio (0.45) (IEA 2024)	Same approach as RI1
Digital Services Energy	Not considered in this setup	Same as RI1
Land Transport Service Level	~30000–39000 (country-specific) pkm/year/cap , or ~80-105 pkm/cap/day (in line with inequality representing a 20:1 ratio between high and low earners)	~12500–21500 (country-specific) pkm/year/cap , or pkm/cap/day (in line with inequality representing a 4.6:1 ratio between high and low earners)
Freight Transport Energy	Scales with passenger transport using global freight-to-passenger energy ratio (0.68) (IEA 2024)	Same as RI1
Aviation Service Level	40,000 pkm/cap/year (~8 continental + 2 intercontinental round trips)	20,000 pkm/cap/year (~4 continental + 1 intercontinental round trips)
Aviation Energy Use	Additional +44 GJ/cap/year (using global avg. energy intensity of 1.1 MJ/pkm)	Additional +22 GJ/cap/year (using global avg. energy intensity of 1.1 MJ/pkm)
Industry Energy	No upper threshold applied; teams to develop own scaling methods	Same as RI1

A3 – Effort sharing

Contemporary deliberations over fairness in mitigation, adaptation and loss and damage rest on foundations laid long before the Paris Agreement. Principles outlined in the 1972 Stockholm Declaration are an example in multilateral environmental policy, navigating the space between sovereign control and a shared duty to avoid harm across borders while recognizing the need for differentiated standards in poorer countries (UN 1972). The 44th UN General Assembly in 1989 was a formative moment where this shared responsibility and differentiation was made explicit in the climate regime, noting the disproportionate role of developed countries in greenhouse gas emissions and calling for cooperation to support developing countries in addressing climate change and its effects (UN 1989).

The UNFCCC in 1992 translated these deliberations into treaty language by grounding action in the principles of equity and in common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities (CBDR&RC), alongside tasking Parties with the common goal to safeguard the climate system for present and future generations (UNFCCC 1992). Later instruments, including the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 and the Paris Agreement in 2015 further developed the operational interpretation of these foundational principles and others. The IPCC's Working Group III (WGIII) has tracked how the interpretation of these principles and their application in evaluating fairness in mitigation, adaptation and loss and damage has evolved across assessment cycles (IPCC 2001, 2007, 2014). Early reports surveyed a range of approaches that continue shape debate today, with examples including equal per capita allocation, effort proportional to historical emissions and economic capacity, global or staged convergence of emissions, and equal cost criteria. The fifth Assessment Report (AR5) organized the literature into categories that remain widely used today. However, despite these advances, bridging divides between countries has been slow, as shown by BASIC expert dialogues and a long record of scholarship, which points to durable disagreements (BASIC experts 2011). These contested deliberations frame political narratives about fairness in mitigation, adaptation and loss and damage till today. See Table A3 for terminology and sources.

In this context, we navigate the precarious task of selecting a marker allocation approach to be considered by all modelling teams, while encouraging the examination of a range of other approaches in model-specific variants. Implementation is generalised to allow a new allocation approach to be considered while keeping the remaining process constant. This generalisation is discussed in the relevant section below, as are a range of sources and interpretations of relevant norms, principles and allocation approaches found in the literature.

We begin with a statement on the principles intended to be addressed in this exercise, namely the principle of CBDR&RC, which is interpreted in the context of the Paris Agreement. This is followed by a definition of the allocation quantity, which implies a delineation between *covered* and *excluded* emissions in the context of our illustrative considerations of fairness and the flexible effort sharing mechanism. *Covered* emissions are those that are considered in assessing fairness and those that define the nature of flexible effort sharing mechanism across regions. *Excluded* emissions in contrast follow a global least-cost trajectory, outside our considerations of fairness and effort sharing. For the purposes of our model intercomparison project, we consider all Kyoto Gases (excluding LULUCF) *covered* emissions and thus consider LULUCF emissions *excluded*.

We exclude LULUCF CO₂ emissions from *covered* emissions in this marker implementation for three reasons that draw from the effort-sharing literature, though we acknowledge this is contested

(Rajamani et al. 2021; van den Berg et al. 2019; Pelz, Ganti, Pachauri, et al. 2025). First, historical LULUCF emission estimates carry substantially larger uncertainty than those for CO₂ from fossil fuels and industry, which propagates directly into fair-share allocations. Second, there is a persistent definitional mismatch between the anthropogenic LULUCF fluxes reported in National Greenhouse Gas Inventories (NGHGs), which count passive CO₂ uptake on managed land, and the scientifically modelled anthropogenic fluxes used in IAM scenarios and global remaining carbon budgets, which do not (Gidden, Gasser, et al. 2023; Weber et al. 2026). Third, IAM frameworks themselves treat LULUCF heterogeneously, with different land-sector modules, which complicates equity-related intercomparison across the JustMIP ensemble precisely because these would propagate into fair-share allocations and would require model-specific harmonisation. We acknowledge that this exclusion is consequential for countries and regions with large land-use emissions or sinks. Treating LULUCF separately, rather than including it under a harmonised allocation rule is the conservative choice for the marker implementation. Modelling teams are encouraged to explore alternative *covered/excluded* delineations as variants so the distributional implications can be assessed ex post. Ultimately, we recognise that this reflects a value judgement and calls for engagement with the requisite equity and justice literature, which we welcome as an additional element to be explored alongside our pioneering effort integrating such considerations into an IAM framework.

Teams are provided code that translates native IAMC reporting variables taken from the respective reference scenario into regional remaining cumulative *covered* emissions allocations from the first native model year depending on the selected allocation approach (<https://github.com/setupelz/fair-shares>). The marker allocation approach we consider here is an equal cumulative per capita allocation from the year 1990 to model horizon. This marker approach is aligned with the principle of CDR but does not consider respective capabilities, nor emissions prior to the year 1990, reflecting a value judgement that can be addressed through the consideration of other variations by modelling teams. The provided code functions with any model regional resolution and starting year. Teams may prepare their own implementations and the code stored in the public repository will be used to verify that regional constraints for the marker allocation approach were correctly implemented after submission.

Teams will ensure that these full-century regional *covered* emissions constraints are respected such that no region overdrafts their allocation by the end of the model horizon. There is no upper limit to the remaining regional allocation in this end year. Teams will also ensure that *excluded* emissions observe the same price trajectory as in the source scenario. This preserves the global policy ambition of the source scenario while introducing regional Covered emissions constraints.

Teams are asked to introduce international climate and development finance mechanisms endogenously in their model frameworks or robustly represent these as ex-post transfers relating a specific ton of CO₂-equivalent (GWP-100, AR6) reduced or avoided internationally in a specific year to the respective price paid and received (representing the effort implied within the model). We propose introducing a global floor on annual international climate and development finance of 100 B USD. In turn, global climate and development finance transfers should not exceed 1% of global GDP (measured in PPP terms), which reflects an upper bound of approximately 2 trillion \$ PPP (in 2024).

[Illustrative implementation approach](#)

Modelling teams are free to implement this approach in a way that fits their own frameworks. For example, this may be applied in three stages as outlined below and described in Figure A5.

1. Run or source the reference scenario without regional effort-sharing constraints. This establishes the benchmark trajectory of emissions, prices, and GDP.

2. Introduce the regional *covered* emissions constraints with no restriction on the volume of international climate finance transfers. This enables the discovery of corresponding carbon price and GDP trajectories under full regional compliance with cumulative allocations and yields a quantified baseline against which limited-cooperation variants are assessed.

3. Convert a candidate GDP share (starting at 0.05%) into an annual physical cap on international mitigation cooperation by dividing the monetary share of each timestep's global GDP (PPP) by the *covered* emission shadow price returned by the unlimited-cooperation run in that timestep. Apply this physical cap as an upper bound on global mitigation cooperation (Gt CO₂/yr) and solve. If the model is infeasible, increase the GDP share in 0.05% increments and retry until the lowest feasible value is reached. Document the final share used.

Figure A5 – Overview of the effort sharing scenario variant implementation.

The resulting relationship between a physical cooperation cap and the implied monetary volume of climate and development finance transfers carries an important upper bound property: whenever the physical cap binds, the new equilibrium raises regional carbon prices in debtor regions (which must do more domestically) and lowers them in creditor regions (which must do less domestically). Because the monetary volume of cooperation is priced at the marginal, and now reduced, creditor-region price, it is necessarily less than the GDP share used to derive the physical cap. This property results in a mono-directional iteration where teams may begin at a low GDP share (0.05%) and increase it in small increments until the model returns a feasible solution, with the assurance that the final monetary volume will remain within the share set. The variance across model teams in the minimum feasible GDP share is an intended feature of this experiment and reflects the combined uncertainty of (i) the minimum technical cooperation requirement and (ii) the model-internal marginal abatement cost.

Table A3 - Principles and norms across the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement as two often cited sources of principles used in deliberations over fairness in mitigation, adaptation and loss and damage contributions.

Principle/Norm	Use	Source
Equity	"...on the basis of equity and in accordance with their CBDR..." / "...to reflect equity and the principle of CBDR&RC, in the light of different national circumstances."	UNFCCC, Preamble & Art. 3(1); Paris Agreement, Preamble & Art. 2(2)
CBDR&RC (in light of different national circumstances)	"Parties should protect the climate system on the basis of equity and CBDR&RC (UNFCCC). The Paris Agreement updates this by adding 'in the light of different national circumstances.'"	UNFCCC, Art. 3(1); Paris Agreement, Preamble & Art. 2(2)
Specific needs & special circumstances (developing)	"The specific needs... of developing country Parties, especially the particularly vulnerable, should be given full consideration."	UNFCCC, Art. 3(2); Paris Agreement, Preamble
Right to / promotion of sustainable development	"Parties have a right to, and should, promote sustainable development... integrated with national development programmes..." / "...global response... in the context of sustainable development and efforts to eradicate poverty..."	UNFCCC, Art. 3(4); Paris Agreement, Preamble & Art. 2(1)
Intergenerational equity	"For the benefit of present and future generations" (UNFCCC) and explicit reference to intergenerational equity in the Paris Agreement's Preamble.	UNFCCC, Art. 3(1); Paris Agreement, Preamble
Precautionary approach	"Where there are threats of serious or irreversible damage, lack of full scientific certainty should not be used as a reason for postponing measures..."	UNFCCC, Art. 3(3)

A4 – Stakeholder interactions and input

Here we document the various inputs and feedback that were provided on the past versions of this protocol. We engaged stakeholders to gather feedback on different elements and stages of the protocol, including input from diverse regional and disciplinary communities.

Table A4 – Overview of stakeholder engagement activities.

Date	Event	Core Purpose / Feedback Summary
28 May 2024	Numbers & Stories 2 – Ethical Dimensions of Climate Change Research	Presented justice framework; broad academic support for integrating justice into models; advised careful communication.
05 Jun 2024	SBSTA – Governance of Carbon Dioxide Removal (Audience: NGOs, negotiators, academia; incl. ELEVATE stakeholder input)	Presented carbon-debt concept; preferences for limited CDR and clear governance.
10 Jun 2024	Klimaaktiv: Austrian Contributions from the Fairness Perspective	Briefed policymakers on carbon debt and national policy implications.
11 Jun 2024	SBSTA Special Event – Evaluation of Policies & Role of Justice in Transformative Policies and Scenario Analysis	Showcased JustMIP approach to justice in policy evaluation and scenarios.
11 Jun 2024	Climate Solutions Summit – Session on Justice in IAMs	Presented JustMIP to broader scientific community.
23–24 Oct 2024	COMMITTED & ELEVATE Modelling & Stakeholder Workshop (India)	Presented carbon debt and JustMIP to Indian scholars/policymakers; generally positive on new protocol.
18 Nov 2024	COP Side Event A Holistic Approach to Climate-Resilient, Just Development: Translating Evidence into Action	Presented JustMIP to policymakers/scholars focused on finance & loss/damage; discussions on effort-sharing and feasibility of financial transfers.
9 Dec 2024	UNEP Webinar (Banking/Financial Community)	Introduced JustMIP to finance sector; raised awareness of justice and carbon-debt concepts.
23 Jan 2025	Co-Creation Workshop on National & Global Net-Zero Strategies (Saudi Arabia)	Justice considerations and carbon debt; feedback to emphasize development dimensions and feasibility of new trajectories.
21 Mar 2025	DLS Expert Webinar #1 – Identifying lines of reasoning	Preference to explore DLS variants via intra-regional inequality (e.g., CEO:unskilled pay ratios); align with SDG10 & CBDR-RC; avoid framing as average consumption cuts; not an income-redistribution experiment; ecological-limits hard to quantify; “regional reference point” seen as arbitrary; well-being literature suggested as qualitative support.
17 Apr 2025	DLS Expert Webinar #2 – Reviewing proposal/methodology	Feedback on operationalizing equity and use of regional reference points; methodological implications.
15 May 2025	DLS Expert Webinar #3 – Implementing in models	Practical implementation and feasibility/quantification issues for DLS assumptions.
20 May 2025	JustMIP for MESSAGE Community Meeting	Technical feedback from modelling community on protocol implementation.

20 Jun 2025	EPICUR Workshop on DLS, PBs, EUE (Vienna)	DLS in JustMIP; feedback from PhDs/postdocs on protocol elements.
20 Jun 2025	Co-Creating Paris-Aligned Pathways: A Stakeholder Dialogue on Justice & Development	Stakeholder co-creation on justice in IAMs. Feedback themes: intergenerational justice as consensus-builder; debate on interspecies/biodiversity; balancing finance for international vs domestic mitigation. DLS/energy: poverty eradication raises demand; acceptance of curbing “luxury” use varies; emphasize co-benefits.
26 Jun 2025	Side Event: Advancing Justice Considerations in Climate Policy – Bridging National and Global Perspectives	Presentation of JustMIP to high-level negotiators; dialogue on bridging national and global justice perspectives in policy and scenarios.
Summer 2025	PRISMA Summer School on Climate Impacts & Equity (PBL/PRISMA)	Feedback on protocol elements from early-career researchers; links to PRISMA work.